

Modelling of Field Capacity from Basic Soil Properties on a Typical Alfisol

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Abstract

The understanding of soil water retention characteristics, including field capacity, plays a pivotal role in various agricultural studies and practices. This knowledge informs the development of irrigation and drainage schedules, assessments of soil water storage capacity (commonly referred to as plant available water), analyses of solute movement, evaluations of plant growth, and assessments of water stress levels. This study the aim of creating a regression model or equation to predict field capacity of soils in a typical Alfisol, which originated from parent material of basement complex, at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm. A total of forty-five (45) disturbed and forty-five (45) undisturbed soils samples were collected along a toposequence (upper, middle and bottom slope) at depths: 0 – 30 cm, 30 – 60 cm and 60 – 90 cm. Soil properties of the disturbed and undisturbed samples were ascertained through standard laboratory techniques and/or calculated utilizing established protocols. The measured soil properties include sand, silt, clay, bulk density, total porosity, field capacity and organic matter. A significant negative relationship between field capacity and bulk density ($r = -0.582$, $P \leq 0.05$) was found and a significant positive relationship between field capacity and total porosity ($r = 0.581$, $P \leq 0.05$) was found. A total of four different models were developed for predicting field capacity of the soil. Model four of field capacity was identified as the best model with the highest R^2 adjusted value of 0.4494. The model explains 45% of variance in the mean square errors of field capacity with sand, bulk density, silt and organic matter contributing statistically to the model.

Keywords: field capacity, regression model, basic soil properties, *Alfisols*

Introduction

Field capacity refers to the maximal water content present in soil after two or three days since saturation, with minimal drainage occurring. This parameter is a measure of maximum amount of water soil can retain for plant use (Hillel, 1998). Historically perceived as a constant soil characteristic, field capacity plays a critical role in assessing water retention and supply properties, determining irrigation requirements, and evaluating soil quality (Lal,

2006; Shao et al., 2006). Optimal plant growth typically coincides with soil water levels maintained close to or at field capacity throughout the plant's growth cycle. Therefore, maintaining soil moisture levels near field capacity is essential for effective irrigation management. As water resources become increasingly valuable, accurately measuring field capacity becomes essential for implementing efficient soil and water management strategies (Madhumita and Verma, 2011).

In the last few years, more researchers have undertaken the creation of models that simulate soil processes. These models serve the dual purpose of enhancing comprehension of crucial soil dynamics and serving as valuable tools for assessing agricultural and environmental challenges. As a result, simulation models have become commonplace in both research and management endeavors (Minasny and McBratney, 2002).

Soil moisture characteristics such as Field capacity (FC) is a fundamental soil characteristic essential for understanding plant water availability, infiltration, drainage, and solute movement. It plays a critical role in various soil water studies. However, directly measuring FC can be expensive, time-consuming, and laborious due to the high variability of soil properties across space and time. Therefore, scholars have developed alternate methods to estimate FC using more readily obtainable soil properties. These properties often include proportions of soil particle sizes (sand, silt, and clay), bulk density, total porosity, and organic matter (OM) content. Many of these estimation methods are referred to as pedotransfer functions (PTFs) as they translate existent, easily measured data into soil hydraulic data (Bouma, 1989). While PTFs are usually developed based on experimental observations, their pertinency can be limited to the specific datasets used in their creation (Donatelli et al., 1996; Wosten et al., 1999). Additionally, different PTFs can generate significantly diverse estimations for the same soil. This variability makes it challenging for users to select the most suitable PTF for their peculiar purposes (Acutis and Donatelli, 2003). Furthermore, PTF estimations often have a moderate level of accuracy. Ideally, PTF predictions would incorporate measures of reliability to enhance user confidence (Schaap et al., 2001).

Soils of the study area have been classified as *Typic Haplustalf*. The region exhibits a mosaic vegetation pattern, alternating between forest and savanna. Gravelly Alfisols are the predominant soil type, reflecting their formation over the basement complex.

Rawls et al. (1982) presented regression equations for the valuation of the soil water content at different water potentials in soils with different particle size distribution. The general form of the linear regression equation is

$$Q_v = a + b \left(\text{sand} \frac{\%}{kg} \right) + c \left(\text{silt} \frac{\%}{kg} \right) + d \left(\text{clay} \frac{\%}{kg} \right) + e \left(\text{organic matter} \frac{\%}{kg} \right) + f \left(\text{bulk density} \frac{kg}{m^3} \right) + g \left(\text{Total porosity} \frac{m^3}{m^3} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where a, b, c, d, e, f and g are regression coefficients.

This study has as an objective to create a regression model or equation for predicting field capacity of soil on a typical Alfisols at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study took place along a toposequence at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm, Ilorin, Nigeria. The toposequence included upper, middle, and bottom slope positions. The dominant vegetation in the location is an intermix of forest and savanna, and the underlying soils formed over basement complex (Olaniyan, 2003). Gravelly Alfisols are the prevalent soil type. While the land has been cultivated in the past, it was fallow during the sampling period. The study area is situated within the Southern Guinea Savanna zone of Nigeria at about 4° 35' East longitude and 9° 29' North latitude. The elevation is 307 meters above sea level. The climate is tropical and characterized by bimodal rainfall featuring peaks in June and September and a break from mid-July to August. Precipitations rate ranges between 1000 mm to 1240 mm per annum. Daily temperatures typically fluctuate between 20°C and 35°C (Kolo *et al.*, 2012).

Soil Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

We collected soil samples at three depths 0-30 cm, 30-60 cm, and 60-90 cm along a toposequence. Fifteen small pits were dug, with five pits located at each position on the toposequence. This resulted in a totality of 90 samples collected (45 undisturbed and 45 disturbed). At each depth, undisturbed core samples were collected using metal cylinders with a height of 8.3 cm and an interior diameter of 5.5 cm. The soil was secured with a piece of calico cloth held in place with a rubber band. The samples were then labeled for identification. Disturbed soil samples were also collected at each depth using a soil auger. These disturbed samples were placed in labeled polyethylene bags. All samples were carried to the laboratory for further analysis of their physical and chemical properties using standard methods.

Soil Samples Preparation

The disturbed samples underwent a process of air drying, crushing, and sieving through a 2 mm mesh before being utilized for analysis.

Soil Properties Analysis

Particle Size Analysis

Particle size analysis was conducted utilizing the hydrometer technique outlined by Gee and Or (2002), with the inclusion of sodium hexametaphosphate (calgon) as a dispersant.

Bulk Density

Bulk density was measured using the core method with oven drying at 105°C to constant weight (Blake & Hartge, 1986). The calculation followed the standard mass-volume relationship:

$$\rho_b = \frac{M_s}{V_t} \quad (2)$$

Where, ρ_b = bulk density ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$),

M_s = Dry soil mass (Kg), and

V_t = Total volume of soil (m^3)

Total Porosity

Total porosity was calculated as:

$$\emptyset = \left[1 - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_s} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where, $\emptyset = \text{Total porosity } \left(\frac{m^3}{m^3} \right)$

$\rho_b = \text{bulk density } \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \right)$,

$\rho_s = \text{particle density assumed to be } 2650 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Soil Organic Matter (OM)

Soil organic carbon content was determined by the Walkley-Black wet oxidation method (Nelson & Sommers, 1982). Following standard practice, the percent organic carbon was converted to estimate total soil OM by multiplying by a factor of 1.724, which reflects the assumption that OM is composed of approximately 58% carbon (Brady & Weil, 1999).

Field Capacity

The determination of field capacity was done by saturating the core samples with water for 24 hours, weighing the samples after three days, and then oven-drying them at 105°C.

$$\text{Percent water at field capacity} = \frac{\text{Weight of saturated soil after three days} - \text{oven dried weight}}{\text{oven dried weight}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

Statistical Tool

Correlation Analysis

In statistics, when two or more variables change together in a predictable way, they are considered correlated.

A multiple correlation was used to investigate the relationship between measured pair of values. The statistical tool is given as:

$$r = \frac{(Z_{ij})(Z_{ik})}{n} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } Z_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j}{S_j} \quad (6)$$

is the standardized values of the response variable X_i .

$$S_j = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j)^2}{n-1}} \quad (7)$$

is the sample variance of the response variable X_i

This correlation coefficient is generally called *Karl Pearson's* coefficient of correlation. Correlation coefficient measures the degree of association (linear relationship) between two or more random variables. Correlation coefficient may be positive or negative. A significant positive correlation coefficient implies that an increase in one variable is accompanied by an increase in the other variable. While significant negative correlation coefficient implies an inverse relationship between the two random variables in question. In

contrast, a non-significant correlation coefficient indicates zero relationship between the variables under study.

A test statistic suggested by Morrison (1976) shall be used to test for significance of this correlation coefficient. This test is given as:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}} \quad (8)$$

where, r is the so called Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient and n is the sample size. It can be shown that when H_0 is true, $t \sim t_{\alpha/2}(n-2)$ (9)

Model Development

Field Capacity

It should be noted that in multiple regression the predictions (independent variables) are assumed to be known without any uncertainty in their given values. Our model can be found useful if some or all of the assumptions hold on the datasets depending on the purpose for which we intend to use it. Because we like to use our models for both estimation and predictions we will investigate all the assumptions and correct necessary violations in the fit of the models.

Majorly, we will use diagnostic plots from the regression models to check assumptions including normality of residuals and presence of potential outliers using "Residuals versus Fitted" charts to show if there is a trend to the residuals and Shapiro-Wilk's test of residuals normality (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) in the R software for statistical computing and graphics (Rcore team, 2013) to confirm residuals normality. Model residuals (error terms) are assumed to be normally distributed if the residual plot shows a random scatter pattern with a consistent spread of residuals around zero for each of the six predictor variables, it suggests a good model fit (Olorede *et al.*, 2013; Olorede and Mudasiru, 2013). When the points in a quantile-quantile plot, especially those in the central region, fall closely along a diagonal line, it suggests that the data are likely normally distributed. We will use standardized residual criterion to check effects of potential outliers in the dataset on the models by removing observations with standardized residuals outside the interval -2.2 according to Barnett and Lewis, 1994; John and Prescott, 1975; and Stefansky, 1972. To assess potential outliers in our models, we will calculate the minimum and maximum residuals for each model. We will then standardize these residuals by dividing them by the corresponding model's root mean square error (RMSE). Ideally, the standardized residuals should fall within a specific range. Values outside this range (expected to be between ± 1 and ± 2) might indicate potential outliers that require further investigation.

All statistical analyses, model fitting and diagnostics shall be done using the language R version 3.0.2 (R Core Team, 2013).

For multiple linear regression models of this type, statistical hypothesis tests regarding the model's parameters can be used to assess the model's effectiveness. We will therefore describe and test hypotheses about parameters of the proposed regression model collectively as well as individually. This will allow us to know if there is significant relationship between the response variables (field capacity) and a subset of the predictors. We will screen the built models based on number of significant parameters, maximum amount of

proportion of variability about the response by these parameters and satisfaction of model assumptions using diagnostic plots as aforementioned.

Rejection of null hypothesis about the full model (model with all parameters) suggests that one or more of the predictor variables significantly impacts the model. Rejection of null hypothesis about individual regression parameter (ANOVA table) indicates that the variable cannot be deleted from the model. Coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) measures extent of decrease in the variability of field capacity gotten by using the 6 predictors in the model. High R^2 alone doesn't guarantee a good regression model. (Myers and Montgomery, 1995). Adding more predictor variables will generally inflate R^2 , even if those variables don't meaningfully contribute to explaining the data's variance. This can lead to models with high R^2 that perform poorly on unseen data. To address this issue, some researchers prefer using *adjusted* R^2 (Myers and Montgomery, 1995).

Generally, R^2_{adj} can actually decrease when adding irrelevant variables to the model. A marked difference between R^2 and R^2_{adj} is a high possibility of the inclusion of irrelevant or statistically insignificant terms. We are also aware of the fact that presence of multicollinearity in the data set will make estimates of coefficients from the least squares fit imprecise and Statistically insignificant (Multivariate Calibrations test by Naes and Martens). If the primary aim is simply to predict the dependent variable (Y) using the X variables, multicollinearity might not be a critical issue. The model's predictions for Y could still be accurate, and the overall R^2 (or adjusted R^2_{adj}) will reflect how well the model fits the data for Y value prediction. However, multicollinearity becomes a significant concern when seeking to understand how individual X variables influence Y. Individual P-values for regression coefficients can be misleading. A high P-value might suggest an unimportant variable, even if it contributes to the overall prediction. The confidence intervals around the regression coefficients become very wide. These intervals may even include zero, making it difficult to determine if an increase in an X variable leads to an increase or decrease in Y. Due to the wide confidence intervals, removing or adding a data point can significantly change the coefficients and even reverse their signs.

Sometimes, multicollinearity can lead to seemingly paradoxical results. The overall model fit (indicated by a low overall P-value) might be good, yet individual X variables lack statistical significance in predicting Y. This occurs because highly correlated X variables provide redundant information. While neither variable may contribute significantly on its own, together they improve the model's fit. Removing them would significantly worsen the overall prediction. Therefore, multicollinearity can lead to a well-fitting model for prediction purposes, but hinder the interpretation of the individual X variables' effects on Y.

Test of Hypothesis about Full Regression Model

Hypothesis 1: [Test of significance encompassing all regression parameters]

Null hypothesis (H_0): The model fits the data/ The model is adequate

Alternative hypothesis (H_0): Not H_0

Or mathematically,

Null hypothesis (H_0): $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_{13} = 0$ [No single predictor showed significant contribution to the model]

Alternative hypothesis (H_0): : $\beta_j \neq 0$ for at least one j [At least one predictor showed significant contribution to the model]

Tests statistic: $F_{ratio} = \frac{MS_{Regression}}{MS_{Error}}$ [Global F-test]

Decision rule: Reject null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis at 0.05 significance level if **P – value** < 0.05, or else do not reject null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2: [Test of significance encompassing individual regression coefficient]

Null hypothesis (H_0): $\beta_j = 0$ [Predictor x_j is not significant given that others are included in model]

Alternative hypothesis (H_0): : $\beta_j \neq 0$ [Predictor x_j is significant given that others are included in model]

Tests statistic: $t_{value} = \frac{\beta_j}{\sqrt{C_{jj}\sigma^2}}$ [Individual t-test]

C_{jj} = diagonal element of the covariance matrix corresponding to β_j

σ^2 = variance of β_j

Decision rule: Reject null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis at 0.05 significance level if **P – value** < 0.05, or else do not reject null hypothesis.

Results

The results of the descriptive statistics obtained for soil properties is presented in Table 1. Results obtained for the Pair-wise correlation of variables measured during field capacity experiment is presented in Table 2. Results of parameter estimates for the models generated for field capacity is presented in Table 3. Results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the multiple regression models created for field capacity are presented in Table 4.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Soil Properties

Soil Properties	Mean	Min	Max	Std dev	C.V
Sand (g/kg)	636.96	400	885	140.15	22.00
Silt (g/kg)	198.73	31	270	70.37	35.41
Clay (g/kg)	166.53	82	350	88.38	53.08
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	1402.36	1065	1698	140.19	10.00
Total porosity (m ³ /m ³)	0.471	0.359	0.598	0.053	11.25
OM (g/kg)	13.12	1.38	27.80	7.40	56.40
Field capacity (%)	44.05	32.26	71.43	11.89	26.99

Table 2. Pair-wise correlation results of variables measured during Field capacity experiment

	Sand	silt	Clay	Bulk density	Total porosity	Field capacity	OM
Sand	1						
Silt	-0.87029266*	1					
Clay	-0.90868682*	0.602503779*	1				
Bulk density	0.08398562	0.01706638	-0.162240647	1			
Total porosity	-0.08358332	-0.017237012	0.161766436	-0.99999666*	1		
Field capacity	-5.8922E-05	-0.114847322	0.079452573	-0.58174566*	0.581464586*	1	
OM	0.667549445*	-0.512282805*	-0.689291767*	-0.00388336	0.003886232	0.187994915	1

* Significant at 5% level when $r \geq 0.293955$

Table 3. Table of Parameter Estimates for Field Capacity Models

Model No.	P-value of Model	Model Multiple R-square value	Model Adjusted R-square value	Coefficients	Estimates	Std. Error	t value	P-value
1.	0.001367	0.4198	0.3282	(Intercept)	5.300e+03	1.115e+04	0.475	0.637
				Clay	-4.361e-01	1.031e-01	-0.423	0.675
				Sand	-8.055e-02	1.026e-01	-0.785	0.437
				Silt	-9.964e-02	1.073e-01	-0.929	0.359
				Bulk Density	-1.981e+00	4.218e+00	-0.470	0.641
				Total Porosity	-5.107e+03	1.113e+04	-0.459	0.649
				OM	4.729e-01	2.868e-01	1.649	0.107
2.	0.0003842	0.4707	0.3849	(Intercept)	7.092e+03	9.801e+03	0.724	0.474
				Clay	-4.141e-02	9.046e-02	-0.458	0.650
				Sand	-8.712e-02	9.009e-02	-0.967	0.340
				Silt	-1.255e-01	9.447e-02	-1.328	0.192
				Bulk Density	-2.653e+00	3.708e+00	-0.716	0.479
				Total Porosity	-6.891e+03	9.784e+03	-0.704	0.486
				OM	3.275e-01	2.551e-01	1.284	0.207
3.	0.0001429	0.5104	0.4288	(Intercept)	7.037e+03	9.356e+03	0.752	0.4569
				Clay	-2.221e-02	8.682e-02	-0.256	0.7995
				Sand	-8.267e-02	8.603e-02	-0.961	0.3430
				Silt	-1.292e-01	9.020e-02	-1.433	0.1605
				Bulk Density	-2.633e+00	3.539e+00	-0.744	0.4617
				Total Porosity	-6.848e+03	9.339e+03	-0.733	0.4682
				OM	4.390e-01	2.490e-01	1.763	0.0864
4.	1.856e-05	0.5021	0.4497	(Intercept)	153.787791	20.408264	7.536	4.69e-09 *
				Sand	-0.065790	0.022221	-2.961	0.005264 *
				Bulk Density	-0.037695	0.009059	-4.161	0.000175 *
				Silt	-0.113318	0.038384	-2.952	0.005384 *
				OM	0.487612	0.232312	2.099	0.042520 *

Table 4. ANOVA Table for Models developed for Field Capacity

Model No.	Source of Variation	Degree of Freedom	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-values	P-values
1.	Clay	1	39.3	39.27	0.4135	0.5241
	Sand	1	185.7	185.73	1.9557	0.1701
	Silt	1	134.7	134.75	1.4189	0.2410
	Bulk Density	1	1941.1	1941.09	20.4391	5.855e-05*
	Total Porosity	1	52.3	52.31	0.5508	0.4626
	OM	1	258.3	258.27	2.7195	0.1074
	Residuals	38	3608.8	94.97		
2.	Clay	1	115.54	115.54	1.5790	0.21678
	Sand	1	400.72	400.72	5.4761	0.02478 *
	Silt	1	193.82	193.82	2.6488	0.11212
	Bulk Density	1	1512.61	1512.61	20.6710	5.67e-05*
	Total Porosity	1	64.46	64.46	0.8808	0.35406
	OM	1	120.61	120.61	1.6482	0.20719
	Residuals	37	2707.49	73.18		
3.	Clay	1	154.44	154.44	2.3161	0.136775
	Sand	1	529.42	529.42	7.9395	0.007807 *
	Silt	1	224.58	224.58	3.3680	0.074748
	Bulk Density	1	1314.34	1314.34	19.7106	8.205e-05 *
	Total Porosity	1	72.79	72.79	1.0915	0.303099
	OM	1	207.30	207.30	3.1088	0.086356
	Residuals	36	2400.56	66.68		
4.	Sand	1	4.10	4.10	0.0638	0.80200
	Bulk Density	1	1748.85	1748.85	27.2203	6.722e-06 *
	Silt	1	426.02	426.02	6.6309	0.01404 *
	OM	1	283.05	283.05	4.4056	0.04252 *
	Residuals	38	2441.42	64.25		

Discussion

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The results obtained in Table 1 for the values of sand, silt and clay contents, bulk density, total porosity, OM and field capacity ranges from 400 to 885, 31 to 270, 82 to 50 g/kg, 1065 to 1698 kg/m³, 0.359 to 0.598 m³/m³, 1.38 to 27.80 g/kg and 32.26 to 71.43%, respectively.

Pair-wise correlation

Sand had negative correlation with silt ($r = -0.870^*$) and clay ($r = -0.909^*$) (Table 2). As sand increases, silt and clay will decrease. Sand was positively correlated with OM ($r = 0.668^*$) as sand increases, OM will increase. Silt was positively correlated with clay ($r = 0.603^*$) and inversely correlated with OM ($r = -0.512^*$) this shows that silt affects OM negatively and as silt increases, clay will also increase. Clay had negative correlation with OM ($r = -0.689^*$) clay affects OM negatively. Bulk density had negative correlation with total porosity ($r = -0.999^*$) and field capacity ($r = -0.582^*$) as bulk density increases total porosity and field capacity decreases Total porosity was positively correlated with field capacity ($r = 0.581^*$) as total porosity increases, field capacity will increase.

Model Development

Four models with p-values < 0.05 were created for field capacity with the corresponding R^2 adjusted values of 0.3282, 0.3849, 0.4288 and 0.4497 for models 1, 2, 3 and 4 as shown in Table 7. Model 4 of field capacity was selected as the best predictive model due to having the highest R^2 adjusted value of 0.4497. This implies that the model fits the field capacity data with the four predictors included after removal of observations with potential outliers and non-significant predictors clay and total Porosity so as to determine the model's prediction accuracy. The model justifies approximately 45% of the variation in mean squared errors of field capacity with sand, bulk density, silt and organic matter being statistically significant contributors to the model.

Examining the significance of each predictor variable in Table 4 for model 4 of field capacity, the results show that we can reject the null hypothesis for bulk density, silt and OM with p-values of 6.722e-06, 0.01404 and 0.04252, respectively. The simple interpretation of this is that each variable is statistically significant within the model when considered alongside the other included variables. This suggests they contribute meaningfully to the model's explanatory power in combination. It does also mean they cannot be excluded. The expression of model 4 as given in Table 3 is expressed in equation (10) as:

$$\hat{Y} = 153.787791 - 0.065790 * \text{Sand} - 0.113318 * \text{Silt} - 0.037695 * \text{Bulk Density} + 0.487612 * \text{Organic Matter} \quad (10)$$

For model 4 of field capacity, the residuals are now normal and there are no potential outliers as shown in Figure 1. In fact, the Cook's distance plot now confirms this by having all the Cook's distances for all the predictors less than 1 as shown in Figure 1. The residuals plot and normal quantile-quantile plots presented in Figure 1 also support this. Normality of the residuals is further confirmed by the histogram presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Diagnostic Plots for Model 4

Fig. 2. Histogram of Model 4 Normal Residuals

The model equation generated for model 4 was used in predicting the field capacity values shown in Table 5. Table 5 presents observed, predicted and residuals of the prediction. The values obtained for observed and predicted field capacity as presented in Table 5 were analyzed for extent of relationship and presented a correlation coefficient of 0.7086. Based on the guideline outlined at <http://www.westgard.com/lesson42.htm> for assessing correlation coefficients, it is observed that when r falls within the range of 0.90 and 1.00, 0.70 and 0.89, 0.50 and 0.69, 0.30 to 0.49, and 0.00 to 0.29 are said to show very high, high, moderate, low, and little if any correlation, respectively. It indicates that field capacity predictions of model 4 of field capacity have high correlation relationship with the observed field capacity values.

The graph of observed and predicted field capacity values is presented in Figure 3. This shows the trend of observed and predicted values of field capacity.

Fig. 3. Graph of Observed versus Predicted Field Capacity

Table 5. Summary of Model 4 Prediction of Field Capacity

Observations	Observed Y (%)	Predicted Y (%)	Residuals ($Y - \bar{Y}$)
1	32.26	33.07635	-0.81635
2	32.26	37.02047	-4.76047
3	38.46	48.16551	-9.70551
4	32.26	33.96041	-1.70041
5	32.26	32.50082	-0.24082
6	57.69	50.70623	6.983774
7	71.43	63.37098	8.059022
8	32.26	38.74145	-6.48145
9	38.46	49.08697	-10.627
10	32.26	38.98002	-6.72002
11	38.46	44.33006	-5.87006
12	38.46	51.89833	-13.4383
13	38.46	46.34247	-7.88247
14	37.31	32.24192	5.068075
15	37.31	27.7532	9.556797
16	57.69	49.4147	8.275303
17	57.69	52.42	5.269999
18	57.69	49.63758	8.052422
19	57.69	53.22095	4.469047
20	57.69	53.8081	3.881896
21	32.26	37.5815	-5.3215
22	38.46	48.55325	-10.0933
23	48.39	33.43684	14.95316
24	38.46	47.08808	-8.62808
25	32.26	40.62179	-8.36179
26	57.69	49.80101	7.888989
27	57.69	49.68176	8.008239
28	57.69	45.74357	11.94643
29	57.69	45.29467	12.39533
30	38.46	40.567	-2.107
31	32.26	41.06191	-8.80191
33	57.69	49.85784	7.832161
34	48.39	34.08673	14.30327
35	32.26	35.84598	-3.58598
36	38.46	46.11329	-7.65329
37	38.46	43.909	-5.449
38	38.46	39.81466	-1.35466
39	38.46	41.38441	-2.92441
40	38.46	41.76351	-3.30351
41	38.46	41.77301	-3.31301
42	38.46	38.70256	-0.24256
43	38.46	39.62808	-1.16808
44	32.26	28.61995	3.640048

Note: Observations 32 and 45 are not included because they contain potential outliers

Conclusion

In the experiment carried out at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm for developing a model for predicting field capacity of the soil, a total of four distinct models were created. Model four of field capacity was chosen as the best model, having the highest R^2 adjusted value of 0.4494. Sand, silt, bulk density and OM was found a fitting option to ascertain soil moisture at field capacity.

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